

Factors Affecting Educational Motivation

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Abstract: This article discusses the factors affecting students' motivation in the educational process and its specific features. Educational motivation is a special type of motivation included in educational activities. In a broader sense, educational motivation can be viewed as a general name for processes, methods, and means of encouraging students to engage in effective cognitive activity and actively assimilate the content of education.

Keywords: motivation, student, education, educational motivation, factor, motive, goal, need, educational process.

Currently, youth education and upbringing in our country is becoming increasingly relevant. Education and upbringing have always been the foundation of societal development. Because a person is at the center of all relationships and connections in society. To achieve the great goals that we must achieve in the future, we must first train highly qualified specialists who meet the demands of the time. The resolution of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PP-3775 "On Additional Measures to Improve the Quality of Education in Higher Educational Institutions and Ensure Their Active Participation in the Large-Scale Reforms Undertaken in the Country" of June 5, 2018, is aimed at this issue.

Improving the education system, enhancing its quality and effectiveness, is closely linked to a number of factors. Proper organization of the lesson process, stimulating students' interest in learning, requires modern educators to possess pedagogical-psychological knowledge and its technologies.

It is necessary to acknowledge that the improvement of students' preparation for professional development in the modern education system is conditioned by many factors of graduate training and the level of their real readiness for professional activity. Among them, the motivation of students in pedagogical universities for learning activities and the perfect mastery of learning strategies in this process are extremely important.

It is known that in science, motivation in a broad sense is considered a complex multifaceted regulator of human life (behavior, activity).

Motivation is a complex, multi-level system of human motivation for activity, embodying needs, motives, interests, ideals, aspirations, attitudes, emotions, norms, and values.

Motivation is a complex structure, a set of forces driving activity, manifested in the form of inclinations, ideals, and directly defining and controlling human activity. Motivation is a set of reasons that motivate a person to engage in active activity. The process of motivation consists of the following psychological processes: perception of the content of the motive, emotional evaluation of its content, understanding and evaluation of the content of the motive, belief in the motive.

Western scholars have given different definitions of the motif. S.L. Rubinstein wrote about the psychological essence of motivation: "Motivation is a set of motives that motivate a person to act, formed through the psyche." Motivation is the force that motivates a person to take action.¹

According to A. Maslow, motivation is the inner desire of a person to engage in a particular activity, linked to the satisfaction of a specific requirement. Motives are a necessary condition for achieving learning effectiveness. Motives for educational activity include all factors that contribute to the manifestation of educational activity: needs, goals, attitudes, a sense of duty, interests, and so on.²

G. Rosenfeld divided the mechanism of learning motivation into the following:³

- ✓ dissatisfaction with learning, activity, or lack of interest in the subject being studied;
- ✓ studying without certain interests;
- ✓ studying for social identification;
- ✓ Studying to achieve success or avoid failure;
- ✓ compulsory or frightened learning;
- ✓ learning based on generally accepted norms or moral obligations;
- ✓ education to achieve a goal in life;
- ✓ education based on social goals, requirements, and values.

The effectiveness of identifying and realizing the student's potential depends on the teacher's skill, their timely assistance, and the ability to establish a collaborative relationship with the student. V.A. Tokareva's research places great emphasis on studying the motives of students' learning activities. In his opinion, artificial situations and conditions are not necessary for a change in learning motives, all of which are shaped in everyday life and in the educational process.

The problem of educational motivation is a traditional research topic in various fields of science, including educational psychology. A.K. Markova argues that knowing the motivational foundations of the educational process is equivalent to knowing the driving force of this process.⁴

No teacher, even a highly qualified teacher, can achieve the desired result if their actions are not coordinated with the motivational foundations of a specific learning process. It should be noted that the problem of educational motivation is one of the main problems of educational psychology. Managing learning motivation allows for the management of the learning process. This problem remains one of the main and most important in psychology and pedagogy to this day. Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate this problem.

Educational motivation is a special type of motivation included in educational activities. In a broader sense, educational motivation can be viewed as a general name for processes, methods, and means of encouraging students to engage in effective cognitive activity and actively assimilate the content of education.

Why is motivation important in education?

For example, motivation allows:

- ✓ Help us focus on what needs to be done;

¹ S.L. Rubinshteyn. Umumiy psixologiya asoslari 1973-yil, 532-b

² A. Maslow "Motivatsiya va shaxsiyat" 1954-yil, http://www.koob.ru/age_psychology/ saytining elektron resursi

³ G. Rozenfeld, Motivatsiyani o'rganish nazariyasi va amaliyoti, 144-b, Berlin 1973-yil.

⁴ Markova A.K. "Talabalarda bilim olishga qiziqishni shakllantirish" 17-b, saytning elektron resursi http://www.koob.ru/age_psychology/

- ✓ allowing us to complete these tasks in a short period of time, as well as to focus for a longer period of time;
- ✓ Minimize distractions and better resist them;
- ✓ remembering and remembering more information;

Achieve results through inner certainty when challenging tasks arise.

Most importantly, motivation motivates us to take action. Without this, it may be difficult or impossible to achieve the desired result. It has been proven that motivation in education has a significant impact on students' academic performance and results.

T.D. Dubovitskaya's methodology "Diagnosis of the Orientation of Educational Motivation" is aimed at studying the educational motivation of students.⁵ There are two scales in the methodology. They are internal motivation and external motivation. The methodology consists of 20 questions, and determining which subjects and determining the number of subjects can change depending on the examiner. Through it, we can determine whether students have higher internal or external motivation than the subjects they are studying. Individuals with a predominance of internal motivation primarily exhibit internal stimuli, needs, and attitudes. Such individuals may have a preliminary interest in the subject being studied or may also appear in the process of studying this subject. If external motivation prevails, it is observed that the student's study of this subject is driven by more external factors.

The following can be identified as factors influencing students' educational motivation in the modular-credit form of education in the higher education system:

The structure of the curriculum involves students knowing the curriculum in advance, i.e., the sequence of topics, the timing of the control, and their training in a specific order. When students feel or see that the curriculum and learning materials are prepared in advance, this gives them a greater sense of security. This, provided in the learning environment, allows students to fully focus on the learning material.

Teachers need to plan lessons and curricula to help students easily assimilate learning materials. All materials used in the lesson should be prepared in advance. Teachers can also present the goals of the course or class at the beginning of the semester or class.

2. The teacher's behavior and personality - it is important that the teacher or mentors are able to better understand the students and help them solve their problems. If a student has negative emotions, such as fear or dislike of their teacher, it can negatively affect their attitude towards science as a whole. If a teacher treats certain students differently or uses derogatory language, this reduces their motivation for learning, leading to cases of discrimination among students.

On the other hand, kindness, attention, positive feedback, and encouragement can have a positive impact on students' motivation to learn.

3. Teaching methodology - if teachers use different teaching methods, students are more likely to maintain their interest in learning. This creates diversity in lessons and prevents boredom among students. Allowing for certain choices, such as ensuring that students work collaboratively in a group, can also lead to good results. The teacher's correct choice of teaching method, explaining the topic through various means during the lesson, contributes to improving the quality of education. As a result of combining teaching methods with the methodology of a qualified teacher, the content and specifics of the subject and the subject under study are fully revealed. This serves as the foundation for the formation and development of students' knowledge, skills, and competencies in the subject.

⁵ T.D. Dubovitskaya "O'quv motivatsiyasining yo'nalganligini tashxis qilish" metodikasi, Psixologiya fanlari va ta'lim 2002-yil, 7-tom. 42-b.

Therefore, the teacher expands the possibility of achieving higher results through the use of various teaching methods.

In some cases, enrollment in extracurricular activities or assistance from a tutor can help students meet their needs that were not met during the lesson.

4. Parent involvement - several habits of parents, such as showing interest in their child's learning material, asking them about how their day was spent, actively listening, helping to complete specific tasks or skills, and attending parent meetings, can indirectly influence children's motivation, particularly internal motivation.

Family problems and instability in the home - the lack of security in the student's home or family problems, in turn, can negatively impact motivation in education. Family conflicts and disagreements lead to a decrease in learning effectiveness. In particular:

- ✓ separation;
- ✓ the absence of one or both parents;
- ✓ not to live with their father or mother;
- ✓ not to have contact with their biological father or mother;
- ✓ frequent movement from one house to another;
- ✓ to be in or participate in child protection services.

As a result, in some cases, additional support from teachers may be required to help resolve family problems.

6. Peer-to-peer relationships are important for students and play an important role in their education and social development. As a person grows up, the influence of peers on them also increases. Therefore, problems and conflicts with peers, their desire to protect their social status among peers, lead to an increase in stress and a decrease in educational motivation. It is important to pay serious attention to the emergence of leadership qualities at this age, the priority of the desire to be recognized in the family, in the social environment.

The educational environment is another key factor influencing the internal environment of the educational process, which refers to various norms and rules that define the educational process.

In a positive environment in the educational process, students feel good, learning is at a level that meets their basic needs, such as "eating daily," and provides an optimal environment for establishing healthy social relationships.

Too many assignments and a very serious learning environment also reduce learning motivation. The complexity of the learning material and learning tasks leads to increased interest in the learning process only when this difficulty can be created or overcome, otherwise interest will quickly decrease.

Adding didactic tools with interesting elements to classrooms helps to soften the atmosphere, improve motivation, and improve results. In addition, allocating enough time for relaxation also has a positive impact on learning motivation.

The evaluation system plays a significant role in increasing students' educational motivation. While standardized assessment increases overall effectiveness, it is likely to have a negative impact on students' motivation to learn. In developed countries, the opposite can be seen, in particular, in the Finnish education system, not only in higher education, but also in the elementary grades of general education schools, students do not undergo any tests. It is no secret that despite the lack of assessment, Finnish children are achieving high academic achievements.

When students are constantly given very difficult tasks and assignments to assess their knowledge, it becomes common for them to lose motivation. This leads to a decrease in students' interest in learning and a decrease in their motivation to learn over time.

One of the important conditions for increasing students' motivation for learning content and academic activities is the creation of opportunities for intellectual independence and initiative in learning. The more diverse and relevant teaching methods are, the easier it is for students to be interested in them. The primary means of arousing sustained interest in learning is the use of questions and assignments that evoke personal motives, the solution of which requires active research from students. Creating a problematic situation plays a crucial role in shaping students' interest in learning, encountering difficulties that they cannot solve with their own knowledge, when faced with a problematic situation, they become convinced that it is necessary to acquire new knowledge or apply the old one in a new situation.

To foster stable, correct, and positive motivation in students, it is necessary to monitor the dynamics of their motivation to acquire knowledge. To achieve this, it is necessary to periodically conduct research to determine the essence of students' learning motivation and establish a dominant motive.

Motivation occupies a central place in every sphere of human life. It encourages people to engage in purposeful activities. Both in professional development and in personal life, it constitutes a complex of human causes and needs, giving impetus to the transformation of needs into opportunities. Motivation is evaluated as a set of motivations and needs that motivate a teacher to successfully implement specific learning activities in their professional activities. In a sense, it is appropriate to consider motivation as a force that manifests a person's abilities.

Motivation is the sum of internal and external driving forces that motivate a person to act, determine the boundaries and forms of activity, and are directed towards achieving specific goals. The influence of motivation on human behavior depends on a number of factors, is largely individual, and can change under the influence of several factors in a person's life.

The importance of solving the problem of educational motivation is determined by its importance for the effective implementation of the didactic process. It is known that a negative or indifferent attitude towards learning can negatively impact a student's poor academic performance or learning activities. Therefore, it is important to know the factors influencing learning motivation in order for students to acquire sufficient knowledge and skills.

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